

III.—*Note on the Bifilar Magnetometer.* By J. A. BROWN, F.R.S.

(Read 7th May 1877).

In a paper on “The Bifilar Magnetometer, its Errors and Corrections,” &c., which appeared in the Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh, vol. xxii. p. 467, it was shown that, in turning the apparatus which carries the upper extremities of the two wires through an angle exceeding by v that through which the lower extremities and the magnet are moved, the upper end of each wire is also turned through an angle greater by v than the lower end. The whole force acting on the magnet, to turn it from the meridian, is compounded of the bifilar and the unifilar torsion—only the former of which had been considered in the method issued by the Committee on Physics of the Royal Society of London for the instruction of directors of observatories.

It was sought in the paper cited to show the change that the neglected forces would introduce into the expression for the unit coefficient, which was found to be

$$k = \cot (v + \beta) \Delta v,$$

instead of

$$k = \cot v \Delta v,$$

where Δv is the arc value of one scale division of the instrument, and β is the variation of v due to the unifilar torsion. There were errors of copying, including omissions in the investigation given. I also remarked, after the paper was printed, that the value of k found was *less* than when the unifilar torsions were neglected (since $\cot (v + \beta) < \cot v$); whereas all the determinations by other methods, in which the unifilar torsions were included, had shown a *greater* coefficient.

Having had some time ago to re-examine questions connected with this instrument, I found that there was an error in the investigation, which I now desire to correct. It was assumed that the right hand side of equation (3) of the paper (equation (1) of this note) might be represented by $G \sin v'$ (where $v' > v$), which cannot be allowed if v varies, especially as v is not small.*

Let us suppose as before, that, in turning the torsion circle carrying the upper ends of the two wires, the horizontal line in which they lie is carried through an angle of $90^\circ + v$, by which means the suspended magnet and the horizontal line passing through the lower ends of the wires are carried through an angle of 90° (that is, the magnet is then at right angles to the magnetic meridian);

* The applications of the formula found (Edinburgh Royal Society Transactions, xxii. p. 468, arts. 5, 6, and 7) are not affected by this error.

the bifilar torsion (that is, the angle made by the upper and lower horizontal lines) will be v , and the torsion of each wire will also be v . If p be the torsion coefficient of a single wire for unity of arc, then the force exerted by the unifilar torsions will be equal to $2pv$; and as the force due to the bifilar torsion is $G \sin v$, the equation of equilibrium will be

$$mX = G \sin v + 2pv \quad . \quad . \quad . \quad (1)$$

where m is the magnetic moment of the magnet, X is the horizontal component of the earth's magnetism, and G is a constant depending on the mass suspended, and length and intervals of the wires.

If now we suppose the magnet to be in the magnetic meridian, and that *each* wire receives a torsion v , so that the magnet is moved from the meridian by an angle δ (the bifilar torsion being zero), then

$$2pv = mX \sin \delta \quad . \quad . \quad . \quad (2)$$

by (1) and (2)

$$mX = \frac{G \sin v}{1 - \sin \delta} \quad . \quad . \quad . \quad (3)$$

Differentiating (1), X and v only being variable, substituting the value of p from (2), and dividing by (3)

$$\frac{\Delta X}{X} = \left\{ \cot v + \sin \delta \left(\frac{1}{v} - \frac{1}{\tan v} \right) \right\} \Delta v \quad . \quad . \quad (4)$$

Since $\frac{1}{v} > \frac{1}{\tan v}$, the coefficient of Δv is always greater than $\cot v$, as has been found in the experiments for this coefficient by deflections and by weights.

Experiments for the value of $\sin \delta$ have shown that equation (4) will give a near approximation to the coefficients by other methods; but the determination may always be vitiated through torsion introduced accidentally into the wires during adjustments. Thus, at Makerstoun, in two early experiments, the unit coefficient, with the same length and interval of wires, was found to be

$$k = 0.0001185,*$$

when the north end of the magnet was turned towards the east; and

$$k = 0.0001522,$$

when the north end was turned towards the west: this difference was found due to torsion existing in the wires. As the methods by deflections, and by varying weights, include all the forces acting, it is much more satisfactory to employ one of these for the determination of the unit coefficient.

* By a typographical error this was given 0.000185 in the Makerstoun Observations (Edinburgh Royal Society Transactions, xvii. part i. p. 37).

The quantity $2pv$ does not affect the unit coefficient only ; it has a much more weighty influence on the temperature coefficient. This was proved experimentally in the paper cited, where, however, it was only shown that the *direction* of the temperature action was such as had been supposed by me previously ; but as the quantities obtained prove also that the *amount* of the action was such as to explain the differences found by the two methods for the determination of the temperature coefficient, I shall examine the results here.

An unmagnetic weight was suspended by two silver wires ; the weight was turned round a vertical axis by the horizontal pull of a small weight hanging at the end of a silk fibre, acting at right angles to the line joining the wires, and passing over a delicate friction wheel.* As the action of currents of air within the box containing the weight produced a regular diurnal movement, the pull was made in the first series of experiments to one side, and in the second series to the opposite side. In the first series, which (from causes indicated) was the least consistent of the two, it was found that an increase of the daily mean temperature within the box (derived from twenty-four hourly observations) corresponded to a movement of the weight in such a direction as to increase the bifilar torsion angle, so that the unifilar torsion force had diminished. In this case the mean reading changed by ± 4.0 scale divisions for $\pm 1^\circ$ Fahr. When, as in the second series, the pull of the small weight was in the opposite direction, an increase of temperature was found as before to coincide with a diminution of the unifilar torsion force, the motion of the weight being also in the opposite direction, the daily mean reading changing by ∓ 2.5 scale divisions for $\pm 1^\circ$ Fahr. Both results confirmed the hypothesis, that the action of an increase of temperature was to diminish the force due to the torsion of the separate wires. It should be remarked, that the total effect of temperature in expanding the wires, and the metal which separates them, is to *increase* the bifilar torsion force, but to *diminish* the bifilar torsion angle, which is just the opposite of the result shown by these experiments.

Taking the result of the second series of experiments as most free from error, we find that one scale division = 0.327 , the angle $v = 65^\circ$, whence employing the approximate coefficient from the bifilar torsion 65° ,

$$\begin{aligned} q &= \cot 65^\circ (\text{arc } 0.327) 2.5 \\ &= 0.00011. \end{aligned}$$

Let us apply this result to the case of the bifilar magnetometer. We know that the effect of increase of temperature on the magnet is to diminish the magnetic moment ; the magnet then moves *from* the north ; the result is as if the earth's magnetism had diminished : the action of increase of temperature on the unifilar torsion of the wires corresponds to a diminution of the force

* See Edinburgh Royal Society Transactions, xxii. p. 472, art. 15.

which turns the north end of the magnet from the north; the magnet will therefore move towards the north. The one action is in just the opposite direction of the other, so that the conjoint action will be the *difference* of the two.

Experiments with hot water on bifilar magnets have shown that a change of 1° Fahr. corresponds to from $q = 0\cdot00022$ to $q = 0\cdot00038$. If we take the mean of the two, the conjoint coefficient, including the action of temperature on the wires, should be

$$q = 0\cdot00030 - 0\cdot00011 = 0\cdot00019;$$

that is, the true coefficient is only about two-thirds of the coefficient by hot water experiments. This is nearly the mean of the results deduced from the determinations of the temperature coefficient by my method of comparisons and by the hot water method (see art. 39 of paper on the Bifilar Magnetometer, previously cited).

I have endeavoured to make this explanation of the cause of the very different results obtained by the two methods as clear as possible, since two of the most eminent magneticians, while accepting the facts, have expressed their inability to offer any explanation of them, though the cause here shown was suggested in my earlier papers on the subject (see Edinburgh Royal Society Transactions, vol. xvi. p. 77, art. 20; Makerstoun Observations for 1843; Edinburgh Transactions, vol. xvii. part ii. p. 53, art. 70).

The conclusions arrived at for the unit and temperature coefficients have been confirmed in every instance in which the two methods for each coefficient have been tried; and it may safely be asserted, that if in any case this confirmation is not obtained, this will be due to some error in the determinations.

I believe that we have at present no more perfect magnetical instrument than the bifilar magnetometer, when proper precautions have been taken in its construction, and when the coefficients have been determined by the methods referred to in this note. It may be remarked, that the wires should be of gold ($\frac{9}{10}$ fine is probably the best), suspended by tubular pincers, and *not* wound on a roller. It is however, also, of the greatest importance that the true temperature of the magnet should be observed, and this can be got only when the thermometer bulb (resting on a thin metal plate) is within the *inner* box near the magnet. Every precaution also should be taken to make the changes of temperature as small as possible.

These precautions are essential if a scientific instrument is required. Biflars with silk suspension threads are not scientific instruments; they are affected by humidity and by unceasing changes in the strain and disposition of the thread fibres, as well as by their frequent rupture, for all of which sources of error no correction is possible.